

COPIM Reading List

Reading that may interest the community that was either discussed in the presenter's talks, previous publications and information about the initiatives they support.

Day 1- Reading

Building platforms, practice, and theory: Copim's interventions into open book publishing

Adema, J & Hall, G, (2013) 'The political nature of the book: on artists' books and radical open access', *New Formations*, vol. 78, no. 1, pp. 138-156. <https://doi.org/10.3898/NewF.78.07.2013>

Adema, J. & Moore, S. A., (2021) "Scaling Small; Or How to Envision New Relationalities for Knowledge Production", *Westminster Papers in Communication and Culture* 16(1), 27-45. doi: <https://doi.org/10.16997/wpcc.918>

Barnes, L. & Gatti, R (2019) "Bibliodiversity in Practice: Developing Community-Owned, Open Infrastructures to Unleash Open Access Publishing." *ELPUB*, 23rd edition of the International Conference on Electronic Publishing, HAL Id: hal-02175276 <https://hal.science/hal-02175276v110.4000/>

Adema, J., Barnes, L., Deville, J., Fathallah, J., Gatti, R., Grady, T., Hopkins, K., Hughes, A., McGann, C., Sanders, K., & Steiner, T. (2024). The Copim perspective on Bibliodiversity. Copim. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.86a892a7>

Anna Tsing. (2012) "On Nonscalability. The Living World Is Not Amenable to Precision-Nested Scales." *Common Knowledge* 18 (3): 507. <https://doi.org/10.1215/0961754X-1630424>

Hart, P., Adema, J., & COPIM. (2022). Towards Better Practices for the Community Governance of Open Infrastructures (1.0). Zenodo., <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6535460>

Radical Open Access Collective. (2025). Publishing Activism within/without a Toxic University. Post Office Press (POP) and Open Humanities Press. <https://doi.org/10.17613/jg2as-46424>

Adema, J & Moore, S. (2024) "Just One Day of Unstructured Autonomous Time': Supporting Editorial Labour for Ethical Publishing Within the University', *New Formations*, vol. 2023, no. 110 & 111, pp. 8-27. <https://doi.org/10.3898/NewF:110-111.01.2024>

Steiner, T. (2023, 4 July). Lost in translation? Revisiting notions of community- and scholar-led publishing in international contexts. ScholarLed Blog.
<https://blog.scholarled.org/lost-in-translation-revisiting-notions-of-community-and-scholar-led-publishing-in-international-contexts/>

Librarians as Diamond Open Access Changemakers

Librarians from Nigeria, Germany, America and England contributed their perspectives on how diamond OA has been facilitated in their institutions.

More about the speakers/ their work

Fatimah J. Abduldayan

[DR. FATIMAH JIBRIL ABDULDAYAN \(MNLA, CLN\) – NMU Library, LIBRARIAN SPOTLIGHT: DR. FATIMAH JIBRIL ABDULDAYAN RECOGNIZED AS LIBRARIAN OF THE MONTH FOR MAY - The Digital Librarian](#)

Martina Benz

[Konstanz Research School \(KRS\) | University of Konstanz , KOPS – Konstanz Online Publication System | Publishing and Open Access | Open Science | Subpages | Communication, Information and Media Centre \(KIM\), Open Access Journals | Publishing and Open Access | Open Science | Subpages | Communication, Information and Media Centre \(KIM\) previous talks- Organising and Financing Diamond Open Access: How can this be Achieved in Collaboration With Others? | ZBW MediaTalk](#)

Jill Cirasella

[Cirasella, Jill | CUNY Graduate Center, Punctum Books Library Program Welcomes New York University Libraries · punctum books](#)

Sarah Thompson

[Sarah Thompson | LinkedIn, Triumphs, Tragedies and Tribulations: An Open Access Retrospective - De Gruyter Conversations, 1.2-sarah-thompson-oipa-june-2024.pptx, Open Access: the triumphs, tragedies and tribulations – an Open Access retrospective – Gold Leaf, 220623-06-uni-of-york-embedding-open-thompson.pdf](#)

Where is the collective funding for open access monographs going?

This was a discussion-based talk from the speakers, see a publication/ interview/ more on each speaker from each below:

Tom Grady (Chair)

[How can we achieve sustainable funding for open access books?](#)

Kira Hopkins

[Kira Hopkins | LinkedIn, Open Access Week 2025 Interview with Kira Hopkins - Copim](#)

Katharina Baier

[Katharina Baier | LinkedIn, Making open access book funding work fairly \(9 May 2024\), CEU Press | Amsterdam University Press](#)

Peter Barr

[-Peter Barr | LinkedIn, Why are universities ending their Elsevier open access agreements? - LSE Impact](#)

Beyond Accessibility

Speakers: Joanne Fitzpatrick (Chair), Tobe Amadi and Anica Zeyen

COPIM resources

[Global Accessibility Barriers · Copim](#)

[Librarians and Open Accessibility · Copim](#)

[Accessibility Tools and Resources · Copim](#)

[09. Open Book Accessib... | Compass](#)

[Our Planning Tool - 10... | Compass - 10 STEP SOAPPT - Open Accessibility Planning Tool](#)

[Our Auditing Tool - OARC | Compass- Open Accessibility Review Checker](#)

Tobe Amadi - Open University

Free course on Digital Accessibility for Academic Libraries -OLCreate:

[PUB_8749_1.0 Digital Accessibility for Academic Libraries: Optimising Primo VE](#)

[Presentation slides- OU Master PowerPoint Template](#)

Anica Zeyen

[Professor Anica Zeyen – Different Ways, Same Purpose, Full article: The disabling marketplace: towards a conceptualisation](#)

Thothally Fresh – Launching Thoth 1.0

[A Thoth Open Metadata Reading List](#)

Day 2 - Reading

Metadata, dissemination challenges & open community solutions for open access books

Speakers: Toby Steiner (Chair), Emma Booth, Edgar Alejandro García Valencia, and Harrison Inefuku

Harrison Inefuku

[Iowa State University Digital Press](#)

[Mississippi River Valley](#)

[Excerpts from Life](#)

[Water is Life](#)

[DESIGNABLE - Advancing Inclusive Design for All](#)

[Transforming Higher Education - Open Education Network](#)

[OER Commons](#)

[Home | Thoth](#)

[What is an academic book publisher? An Ibero-American contribution to the definition | Insights](#)

Emma Booth

[Emma Booth \(she/her\) Twitter | Linktree](#)

[International Metadata Recommendations, and Platform-Specific Requirements for Open Access Books and Chapters](#)

[Joint Statement on the Metadata Rights of Libraries | ICOLC Website](#)

[About — COMET](#)

Archiving and preserving PhD theses: Implications for open access

Speakers: Jenny Fry (Chair), Simon Bains, Jenny Basford, and Zoe Stockdale

[Archiving & Digital Preservation · Copim](#)

[Scoping PhD Theses: Some initial reflections - Copim](#)

[Digitally Endangered Species: The BitList](#)

Simon Bains

[Aberdeen 2040 Strategic Planning | StaffNet | The University of Aberdeen](#)

[Data protection: The UK's data protection legislation - GOV.UK](#)

[Digital preservation advice and consultancy - Jisc](#)

[Digital preservation – more than just storage - Jisc](#)

[Preserving tomorrow's history today with new digital partnership | News | The University of Aberdeen](#)

[Digital Preservation Solutions | Libnova](#)

[Libsafe GO: Cloud Digital Preservation | Libnova](#)

Zoe Stockdale

[Zoe Stockdale | LinkedIn](#)

[Supervisor development plan - All modules | Learn](#)

Holly Turpin

[Archiving and Preserving My PhD Thesis: Reflections for Further Research – Open Research](#)

Experimental publishing futures

Speakers: Janneke Adema (co-chair), Simon Bowie (co-chair), John Atkinson, Emma Gallon (online), and Paul Stevens

Janneke Adema

[Publishing as a Relational Practice: Radical Open Access and Experimentation - Living Books](#)

Emma Gallon

- [University of London Press \(UOL\) -About us - University of London Press](#)
- [Manifold platform- Manifold | Manifold Possibilities](#)
- **Example book projects:**
 - [*Reframing Failure in Digital Scholarship - Reframing Failure in Digital Scholarship | University of London Press*](#)
 - [*Women Working the Past: Archaeology, History and Heritage in Britain, 1870–1950- Women Working the Past: Archaeology, History and Heritage in Britain, 1870–1950, Thornton, Harloe*](#)
 - [*Living with Machines: Computational Histories of the Age of Industry- Living with Machines | University of London Press*](#)

John Atkinson

- [University of Westminster Press \(UWP\)- Home | University of Westminster Press](#)
- [I used to love to dream- https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.11738372](https://doi.org/10.3998/mpub.11738372)
- [Liverpool University Press](#)
- [Deep Maps Project- Deep Maps: Blue Humanities](#)

[Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project 'Deep Maps: Blue Humanities' - Copim](#)

Where are the new scholar-led open access presses & how can we support their emergence? Speakers: Lucy Barnes (Chair), Julien McHardy, Niki Rhyner And Zoe Wake Hyde

[Official Launch of the Experimental Publishing Compendium - Copim](#)

Julien McHardy

[Home](#)

[About – Mattering Press](#)

Niki Rhyner

[M.A. Niki Rhyner — Chair for the History of Science](#)

[About - intercomverlag - Verlag für neue Publikationsformate](#)

Zoe Wake Hyde

[Radish Press](#)

[Passion for Publishing: talking OMP with Coordinator Zoe Wake Hyde](#)

Closing keynote: Scholarly Book and the Digital Commons, Siddharth Soni

[The Chancellor, Masters & Scholars Of ... vs Rameshwari Photocopy Services & Ors. on 9 December, 2016](#)

[Moore, S. \(2025\) Publishing Beyond the Market, Open-Access, Care, and the Commons,](#)

[University of Michigan Press, available at: https://doi.org/10.3998/](#)

- **[Adema, J. and Moore, S.A. \(2023\) 'Just One Day of Unstructured Autonomous Time': Supporting Editorial Labour for Ethical Publishing within the](#)**

University, New Formations, 2023 (110 & 111), 8-27.

<https://doi.org/10.3898/NewF:110-111.01.2024>

- **[Translations \(1980\) | QUB](#)**
- **[Intellectual Property Rights as Means and Mechanism of Imperialism \(Chapter 7\) - Science, Colonialism, and Indigenous Peoples](#)**
- **[Public enemies and private intellectuals: Apartheid USA - Ruth Wilson Gilmore, 1993](#)**
- **<https://www.minorcompositions.info/wp-content/uploads/2013/04/undercommons-web.pdf>**